
ESTIMATING ABSOLUTE WEB CRAWL COVERAGE FROM LONGITUDINAL SET INTERSECTIONS

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ABSTRACT

Web archives preserve portions of the web, but quantifying their completeness remains challenging. Prior approaches have estimated the coverage of a crawl by either comparing the outcomes of multiple crawlers, or by comparing the results of a single crawl to external ground truth datasets. We propose a method to estimate the absolute coverage of a crawl using only the archive’s own longitudinal data, i.e., the data collected by multiple subsequent crawls. Our key insight is that coverage can be estimated from the empirical URL overlaps between subsequent crawls, which are in turn well described by a simple urn process. The parameters of the urn model can then be inferred from longitudinal crawl data using linear regression. Applied to our focused crawl configuration of the German Academic Web (15 semi-annual crawls between 2013–2021), we find a coverage of approximately 46% of the crawlable URL space for the stable crawl configuration regime. Our method is extremely simple, requires no external ground truth, and generalizes to any longitudinal focused crawl.

Keywords: web archive, crawl coverage, set intersection, longitudinal analysis, sampling fraction

1 Introduction

Focused web crawls—archives targeting specific domains like academic institutions, government websites, or cultural heritage—must terminate at some point. The German Academic Web (GAW), for instance, crawls approximately 150 German university seeds semi-annually, stopping after collecting roughly 100 million records. This raises the question: how much of the *crawlable* German Academic Web (cGAW) is archived by the GAW?

A web crawl is defined by its crawl configuration, which specifies the heuristics and rules to collect websites. For instance, it defines the termination threshold M , i.e., the total number of URLs to be collected in the crawl. What remains unknown, however, is the set of URLs (N) that could, in principle, be collected by a given crawler and its crawl configuration. As a result we are faced with the fundamental limitation of a single, isolated crawl: it does not allow us to determine its coverage $c = M/N$ of the underlying web, i.e. it remains unknown how much of the crawlable web space does it actually capture.

Several strategies have addressed related problems. Bharat and Broder [1998] estimated *relative* search engine sizes by comparing URL sets across multiple engines. Their method yields ratios like “Engine A is $2.3\times$ larger than Engine B” but cannot determine what fraction of the total web either captures. Entity-based approaches use external ground truth (e.g., named entities from reference databases) to measure recall of known items. This requires domain-specific datasets and measures coverage only for that entity class, not the full URL space. Quality frameworks like SHARC [Denev et al., 2011] assess temporal coherence and resource completeness of archived pages, but not overall domain coverage.

Here we provide an interpretable method to estimate absolute coverage from longitudinal crawl data alone. The contribution is twofold. First, we gain theoretical insight by modeling the crawling process using a simple urn model. And second, we estimate coverage by fitting the model the longitudinal crawl data.

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Table 1: Positioning of our approach relative to prior work.

Method	Output	Requirements
Bharat & Broder (1998)	Relative: $\frac{\text{Size}(A)}{\text{Size}(B)}$	Multiple crawlers
Paris & Jäschke (2020)	Recall of entity class	External ground truth
This paper	Absolute: $c = M/N$	Only longitudinal data

The remainder of the paper is structured as follows. Section 2 reviews related work on set similarity measures and coverage estimation. Section 3 formalizes the random sampling model and derives the self-intersection interpretation. Section 4 applies our method to the German Academic Web, showing the heatmap, observed decay patterns, and coverage estimates. Section 5 discusses implications and limitations.

2 Related Work

Our work has strong connections to previous contributions that developed measures for comparing collections. The Jaccard index $J(A, B) = |A \cap B| / |A \cup B|$ [Jaccard, 1901] and the Dice-Sørensen coefficient $D(A, B) = 2|A \cap B| / (|A| + |B|)$ [Dice, 1945, Sørensen, 1948] are symmetric measures originally developed for ecological comparison. Broder [1997] introduced the *containment* measure $C(A, B) = |A \cap B| / |A|$, which is asymmetric and directly interpretable as “the fraction of A contained in B .” This is the measure we adopt, as it connects naturally to sampling fractions under our urn model. Garg et al. [2015] showed that asymmetric similarity measures often outperform symmetric ones in retrieval tasks. Bharat and Broder [1998] pioneered the use of set intersections to estimate search engine coverage. By sampling URLs from one engine and checking their presence in others, they computed pairwise overlap fractions and derived relative size ratios. Their key formula— $\text{Size}(A) / \text{Size}(B) = \Pr(A \cap B | B) / \Pr(A \cap B | A)$ —is a form of capture-recapture estimation. However, this approach yields only relative sizes and requires multiple independent crawlers. Henzinger et al. [2000] studied near-uniform URL sampling using random walks, addressing biases in web graph traversal. The Lincoln-Petersen estimator from ecology [Lincoln, 1930] provides a theoretical foundation for population estimation from marked samples, though it assumes closed populations. Our theoretical grounding comes from urn model theory. Kalinka [2013] derived probability mass functions for intersection sizes when sampling from urns, showing that the expected intersection under independent sampling follows the hypergeometric distribution. Mahmoud [2008] provides comprehensive treatment of Pólya urn models and their applications to discrete sampling problems. Tsagkias et al. [2011] demonstrated applications of hypergeometric distributions in information retrieval. The SHARC framework [Denev et al., 2011] introduced quality measures for web archives focusing on “blur” (single-visit capture quality) and “coherence” (temporal consistency across captures). Brunelle et al. [2015] studied archive damage through missing embedded resources. Ainsworth et al. [2015] analyzed temporal coherence of archived web pages. These works focus on capture quality rather than coverage estimation. Koehler [2002], Koehler et al. [2004] conducted foundational longitudinal studies finding that web page half-life is approximately two years, with persistence varying by domain type (.gov pages persist longer than .com). Gomes and Silva [2006] developed logarithmic models for URL persistence, distinguishing between URL death and content change. Fetterly et al. [2003] studied large-scale web evolution, quantifying change rates across millions of pages. Wren [2008] analyzed URL decay in academic citations, finding that multiply-cited URLs persist longer. These studies inform our interpretation of the decay parameter α but do not address coverage estimation. In a recent interview study by Baack [2024], the Common Crawl team expressed fundamental uncertainty about web coverage, with their director noting the web is “practically infinite” and that “even defining what you mean by comprehensiveness is a task in itself”.

Overall, existing work either (1) uses entity-based proxies requiring content analysis and external datasets; (2) compares multiple crawlers to obtain only relative sizes; or (3) studies temporal decay without connecting it to coverage estimation. Our contribution is to show that absolute sampling fractions can be extracted from longitudinal self-intersections of a single archive, decomposing coverage from decay in a single model. We apply these insights to the GAW.

3 Theoretical intuition and urn model

Let u_t denote the set of URLs captured in a given crawl at time t , with $|u_t| = M$ being the number of URLs captured in the crawl. Furthermore, let N denote the size of the crawlable web, which is represented by the size of the set of all URLs within the archive’s scope that could potentially be harvested. Note that while we assume to know the value of M , we do not have access to the value of N , as a crawl will not capture all crawlable URLs. The ratio $c = M/N$ is defined as the coverage of the crawl.

The urn represents a population of N unique URLs. Time advances in discrete steps $t = 1, \dots, T$, which corresponds to successive crawls. At each time step, the urn process consists of two steps: First, turnover occurs in the underlying population. This means that a fraction of $(1 - \alpha)$ of the N URLs is removed and replaced by the same number of newly introduced URLs, such that N remains constant. In other words, the parameter $\alpha \in [0, 1]$ captures the temporal persistence of URLs across two subsequent crawls. Second, conditional on the resulting population, a crawl sample u_t is generated by drawing M URLs uniformly at random without replacement from the urn.

Crucially, this simple model allows us to derive an analytical expression for the overlap between two crawl at different times, u_i and u_j . First, let us consider an arbitrary URL that appears in the crawl at time $t = 1$. The probability that this URL survives the population turnover for $T - 1$ steps is α^{T-1} . Second, conditional on surviving until time T , the probability that it is included in the crawl at time T corresponds to M/N , i.e., the uniform sampling probability from the urn. Since the initial crawl contains M URLs, the expected size of the overlap between the first and the T -th crawl is therefore given by

$$\mathbb{E}[|u_1 \cap u_T|] = M \cdot \alpha^{T-1} \cdot \frac{M}{N} = \frac{M^2}{N} \alpha^{T-1}. \quad (1)$$

Dividing by M , and substituting $c = M/N$, yields the expected fraction of URLs in the initial crawl that reappear at time T ,

$$f(T) = c \alpha^{T-1}. \quad (2)$$

The important feature of Eq. 2 is that it can readily be used to fit the empirical observations of temporal crawl overlaps to extract the value of c . Interestingly, Eq. 2 is closely linked to previous work, specifically, Broder’s containment measure, defined as [Broder, 1997]

$$g(u_i, u_j) = \frac{|u_i \cap u_j|}{|u_i|}. \quad (3)$$

As defined in Eq. 3, $g(u_i, u_j)$ denotes the fraction of crawl u_i that also appears in crawl u_j , and has been used for cross-sectional multi-engine comparisons Bharat and Broder [1998]. In contrast to its original conception of g , our model allows to interpret Eq. 3 as the definition of URL overlap between two crawls separated by $t = i - j$, hence

$$g^* = g(u_i, u_i), \quad (4)$$

is interpreted as “self-intersection”, which we recover from Eq. 2 by setting $T = 1$ and thus get $g^* = c$. Equivalently, this result can be obtained directly from Eq. 3 by assuming two independent draws ($i = j$) of size M from a population of N URLs, where the expected intersection size follows from the hypergeometric distribution [Kalinka, 2013], i.e., we get²

$$g^* = \mathbb{E}\left[\frac{|u_1 \cap u_T|}{M}\right] = \frac{1}{M} \frac{M^2}{N} = c. \quad (5)$$

Importantly, this interpretation holds even if the crawl itself is non-uniform. Consider a fixed crawl u with $|u| = M$ obtained by any sampling method (uniform, breadth-first, preferential, etc.) from population U with $|U| = N$. If we compare against a uniform sample \hat{u} from U , the expected intersection is:

$$\mathbb{E}\left[\frac{|u \cap \hat{u}|}{M}\right] = \frac{M}{N} = c. \quad (6)$$

This follows because each element of u has probability M/N of being sampled into \hat{u} , regardless of how u was constructed. Equivalently, a uniform sample of size M would contain $c \cdot M$ elements in common with the crawl.

Thus the coverage estimate c has three equivalent interpretations: (i) the fraction of the cGAW captured by the crawl, (ii) the expected overlap fraction with a uniform sample, and (iii) the normalized self-intersection under independent resampling.

Extending this framework to pairs of crawls, we compare the observed relative overlap $g(u_i, u_j) = |u_i \cap u_j|/M$ against the theoretical baseline of uniformly sampled counterparts, denoted \hat{u}_i and \hat{u}_j . Under the urn model with independent uniform sampling, the expected relative overlap is determined solely by the coverage c and the temporal decay α :

$$\mathbb{E}[g(u_i, \hat{u}_j)] = \mathbb{E}[g(\hat{u}_i, \hat{u}_j)] = c \cdot \alpha^{|i-j|} \quad (7)$$

²Note that the hypergeometric (sampling without replacement) and binomial (independent Bernoulli trials) models give identical expected intersections. They differ only in variance—hypergeometric variance is smaller by the finite population correction $(N - M)/(N - 1)$. For point estimation, the models are equivalent.

Figure 1: Pairwise URL set intersections for the 15 GAW crawls. (a) The heatmap reveals temporal decay structure; the diagonal shows estimated self-intersection values. (b) Log-transformed containment vs. time difference exhibits a linear relationship.

However, real-world crawling processes often exhibit temporal correlations - for instance, through persistent seeds that force the crawler into the same local subgraph across repetitions. We model this deviation by introducing a *crawler bias coefficient* R_{ij} , defined as the ratio between the actual and theoretical expectations:

$$R_{ij} = \frac{\mathbb{E}[g(u_i, u_j)]}{\mathbb{E}[g(u_i, \hat{u}_j)]} = \frac{\mathbb{E}[g(u_i, u_j)]}{c \cdot \alpha^{|i-j|}} \tag{8}$$

The overlap ratio R_{ij} serves as a diagnostic metric for crawler behavior: $R_{ij} \approx 1$ implies a uniform process, while $R_{ij} > 1$ reveals positive correlation where the crawler systematically revisits specific subgraphs. This bias is empirically isolated as the residual term in the log-linear regression:

$$\underbrace{\log R_{ij}}_{\text{Residual}} = \log g(u_i, u_j) - (\log c + |i - j| \log \alpha) \tag{9}$$

4 Results

We apply our methodology to the German Academic Web (GAW), a longitudinal focused crawl of German university websites. The part of the GAW considered here consists of 15 semi-annual focused crawls conducted between December 2013 and December 2021. Each crawl started from approximately 150 seed domains corresponding to German universities with doctorate-granting rights. The Heritrix crawler Internet Archive was used with a breadth-first traversal policy. Crawls terminate after collecting approximately 100 million records Paris and Jäschke [2020].

The data of our longitudinal crawls of the cGAW allows us to empirically observe the containment between two crawls $g(u_i, u_j)$ for $i > j$. The results are depicted in Fig. 1, which shows two views of the pairwise containment measures. Figure 1(a) displays the 15×15 matrix of $g(u_i, u_j)$ values as a heatmap. The off-diagonal entries show clear temporal structure, and values decrease with distance from the diagonal, i.e. for increasing time difference between two crawls, reflecting URL turnover. This visualization makes explicit our estimation target, namely the hypothetical intersection of two independent samples drawn at the same moment, i.e., $\Delta t = 0$. Figure 1(b), depicts a scatter plot showing the log-transformed containment measure $\log g(u_i, u_j)$ as a function of the time difference between two crawls for every crawl pair.

For the GAW, the observed decay is in excellent agreement to our model, as depicted in Fig. 2(a), where we have fitted Eq. 2 via ordinary least squares regression to the log-transformed containment values ($R^2 = 0.95$). In particular, we find an average decay rate of $\alpha \approx 0.73$ per year, which corresponds to approximately 27% annual URL turnover, consistent with prior studies of web persistence Koehler [2002]. Most importantly, we estimate coverage as 0.46, i.e., an average of 46% of the complete crawlable academic web are captured. To demonstrate the validity of the analytical expression of the urn model, we compare Eq. 2 with stochastic simulations of the model in Fig. 2, which show perfect agreement.

Figure 3 examines whether coverage varies over time by fitting separate regressions for each crawl’s comparisons with all subsequent crawls. Panel 3a depicts the individual regression lines and show consistent decay behavior with

Figure 2: Validation via simulation. (a) Regression on GAW data. (b) Simulation with urn model parameters recovers the same relationship, confirming the method.

Figure 3: Per-crawl regression analysis. (a) Separate regressions for each starting crawl yield approximately parallel lines. (b) The y-intercept (estimated c) shows a rising trend over 2013–2021.

approximately parallel slopes. Panel 3b presents the y-intercepts estimating the sampling fraction c for each starting crawl. This shows a rising trend over time in, indicating that crawl coverage has improved over the observation period. This improvement in coverage is either driven by an increase in crawl efficiency or a reduction in the crawlable population size N .

5 Discussion

Estimating web crawl coverage can be very challenging and constrained by the way web data is crawled. We presented the first method to estimate absolute web crawl coverage from longitudinal data alone, i.e., from a series of subsequent crawls. By analyzing pairwise URL set intersections over time across crawls we were able to estimate the coverage of the crawls. A simple urn model reproduces key features of the empirical data and therefore provides theoretical grounding for our ability to estimate coverage from the longitudinal GAW crawl data.

The key insight is that temporal variation in a longitudinal archive of web crawls serves as a substitute for the multiple independent samples required by traditional capture-recapture methods. In particular, by observing how URL sets overlap across time, the urn model allows us to decompose the (i) coverage (y-intercept of the fitted log relationship c (i.e. what fraction of the total we capture), and the (ii) decay component α , slope of the log relationship, i.e., how quickly content turns over. As a case study, we use our method to estimate our coverage of the German Academic Web. We find that each crawl captures approximately 46% of the complete crawlable academic web, with content persistence of approximately 73% per year (27% annual URL turnover).

Our work extends Bharat and Broder [1998] from cross-sectional comparison of search engine indices to longitudinal analysis of crawled URL sets. Where they probed multiple search engines through query interfaces and could only compute relative sizes, we extract absolute coverage from direct temporal self-intersections within a single crawl archive. Furthermore, our extracted decay parameter $\alpha \approx 0.73$ per year—representing the annual URL persistence rate—implies a half-life of approximately 2.2 years for URL survival, closely aligning with Koehler [2002]’s longitudinal finding of approximately 2-year half-lives for web page persistence.

The method enables ongoing assessment of crawl coverage without external resources. Specifically, it provides archive operators a self-contained method to assess coverage without knowledge of external ground truth datasets, content extraction or entity matching, and most importantly, without the ability to compare to other crawlers. Researchers may benefit by being able to estimate what fraction of the target web it captures, informing confidence in downstream tasks i.e. training LLMs. In addition, the temporal stability analysis (Fig. 3b in Section 4) reveals whether the target population is in a “replacement regime” (stable size) or “growth regime” (expanding), guiding crawl frequency decisions.

The way a crawl is modeled here is independent of the type of flux in the URL space, the flux of the web only affects how we may fit the overlap data. Corresponding the y-intercept to the crawl size normalized self-intersection is independent of the flux. If the cGAW grows over time, the sampling fraction $c_t = M/N_t$ decreases. We would observe the coverage estimate declining. Conversely, if N_t shrinks, coverage estimates would increase. The coverage estimate across starting years provides an internal test for dynamics of N_t . In the case of the GAW, with a non-revisit policy, the web is crawled outwards, exploring further regions without resampling previously seen URLs. The sampling bias is accounted for through the log residual, providing a measure for an intersections deviation from the urn model.

Like any inference based on indirect observation, our approach rests on a set of assumptions and data requirements that delimit its applicability. We therefore discuss key limitations and boundary conditions below. The method assumes crawls sample approximately uniformly from the cGAW. Real crawls exhibit biases: breadth-first traversal favors well-connected pages; scope restrictions exclude content outside seed domains. The coverage estimate should be interpreted as coverage weighted by the crawl configuration, not uniform coverage of all theoretically reachable URLs. The approach further requires multiple crawls over time. It cannot assess coverage of a single snapshot. Archives with a small number of crawls may have insufficient data for reliable inference of the crawl coverage. We also assume the cGAW size remains approximately constant between start and termination of a crawl. In rapidly growing domains (e.g., social media), this assumption may not hold, and the intercept interpretation would be confounded by population change. Finally, coverage is measured at the URL level, not content level. A URL may persist while its content changes substantially. Content-based similarity measures could complement URL intersection analysis.

Several extensions merit investigation. First, the urn model could be generalized to account for non-uniform sampling by incorporating weights that reflect crawl bias toward highly connected or frequently updated pages (i.e., a network-based approach). Second, the method could be applied to other longitudinal web archives, such as Common Crawl, or domain-specific collections, to assess its generality across crawl regimes. Third, URL-level intersection could be complemented with content-based similarity measures (e.g., MinHash) to estimate semantic rather than purely URL-level coverage. Finally, future work could develop diagnostics to disentangle true population growth from declining coverage in longitudinal archives.

In conclusion, we introduced a self-contained method to estimate absolute web crawl coverage using longitudinal data alone, leveraging temporal self-intersections of URL sets as a substitute for independent samples. By modeling overlap dynamics with a simple urn process, we showed that the intercept of the empirically observed decay in containment directly recovers the sampling fraction, while the slope captures content turnover. Applied to the German Academic Web, the method indicates that individual crawls capture approximately 46% of the crawlable URL space, with an annual persistence rate of about 73%. Because the approach requires neither external ground truth nor comparison across crawlers, it provides archive operators and researchers with an interpretable and general tool for assessing crawl completeness in longitudinal web archives.

Data availability. Metadata for the German Academic Web (URLs and timestamps) is available at <https://german-academic-web.de/>.

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References

- Scott G Ainsworth, Michael L Nelson, and Herbert Van de Sompel. Only one out of five archived web pages existed as presented. In *Proceedings of the 26th ACM Conference on Hypertext and Social Media*, pages 257–266. ACM, 2015.
- Stefan Baack. A critical analysis of the largest source for generative ai training data: Common crawl. In *Proceedings of the 2024 ACM Conference on Fairness, Accountability, and Transparency*, pages 2199–2208, 2024.
- Krishna Bharat and Andrei Broder. A technique for measuring the relative size and overlap of public web search engines. *Computer Networks and ISDN systems*, 30(1-7):379–388, 1998.
- Andrei Z Broder. On the resemblance and containment of documents. In *Proceedings of the Compression and Complexity of Sequences*, pages 21–29. IEEE, 1997.
- Justin F Brunelle, Mat Kelly, Hany SalahEldeen, Michele C Weigle, and Michael L Nelson. Not all mementos are created equal: measuring the impact of missing resources. In *International Journal on Digital Libraries*, volume 16, pages 283–301. Springer, 2015.
- Dimitar Denev, Arturas Mazeika, Marc Spaniol, and Gerhard Weikum. The sharc framework for data quality in web archiving. *The VLDB Journal*, 20(2):183–207, April 2011. ISSN 1066-8888. doi:10.1007/s00778-011-0219-9. URL <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00778-011-0219-9>.
- Lee R Dice. Measures of the amount of ecologic association between species. *Ecology*, 26(3):297–302, 1945.
- Dennis Fetterly, Mark Manasse, Marc Najork, and Janet Wiener. A large-scale study of the evolution of web pages. *Software: Practice and Experience*, 34(2):213–237, 2003.
- Ankita Garg, Catherine G Enright, and Michael G Madden. On asymmetric similarity search. In *2015 IEEE 14th international conference on machine learning and applications (ICMLA)*, pages 649–654. IEEE, 2015.
- Daniel Gomes and Mário J Silva. Modelling information persistence on the web. pages 193–200, 2006.
- Monika R Henzinger, Allan Heydon, Michael Mitzenmacher, and Marc Najork. On near-uniform url sampling. *Computer Networks*, 33(1-6):295–308, 2000.
- Internet Archive. Heritrix – The Internet Archive’s open-source, extensible, web-scale, archival-quality web crawler project. <https://github.com/internetarchive/heritrix3>. [Online; Last accessed 1 Apr 2020].
- Paul Jaccard. Étude comparative de la distribution florale dans une portion des alpes et des jura. *Bulletin de la Société vaudoise des sciences naturelles*, 37:547–579, 1901.
- Alex T Kalinka. The probability of drawing intersections: extending the hypergeometric distribution. *arXiv preprint arXiv:1305.0717*, 2013.
- Wallace Koehler. Web page change and persistence—a four-year longitudinal study. *Journal of the American society for information science and technology*, 53(2):162–171, 2002.
- Wallace Koehler et al. A longitudinal study of web pages continued: a consideration of document persistence. *Information Research*, 9(2):9–2, 2004.
- Frederick C Lincoln. Calculating waterfowl abundance on the basis of banding returns. *US Department of Agriculture Circular*, 118:1–4, 1930.
- Hosam M Mahmoud. *Pólya urn models*. CRC Press, 2008.
- Michael Paris and Robert Jäschke. How to assess the exhaustiveness of longitudinal web archives: A case study of the german academic web. In *Proceedings of the 31st ACM Conference on Hypertext and Social Media*, pages 85–89, 2020.
- Thorvald Julius Sørensen. A method of establishing groups of equal amplitude in plant sociology based on similarity of species content and its application to analyses of the vegetation on danish commons. *Biologiske skrifter*, 5:1–34, 1948.
- Manos Tsagkias, Maarten De Rijke, and Wouter Weerkamp. Hypergeometric language models for republished article finding. In *Proceedings of the 34th international ACM SIGIR conference on Research and development in Information Retrieval*, pages 485–494, 2011.
- Jonathan D Wren. Url decay in medline—a 4-year follow-up study. *Bioinformatics*, 24(11):1381–1385, 2008.